

GENERALIZATION AND CONCRETIZATION**Karimova O`g`iloy Rahmatulla qizi**

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Abstract. *Lexical transfer operation as defined by Klaudy (2003) is a collective term for all the systemic and routine-like operative moves developed by generations of translators to handle the difficulties stemming from the different lexical systems and cultural context of the two languages functioning together in the process of translation. The paper deals with two lexical operations carried out by translators in Indo-European-Hungarian translation: narrowing (or specification, concretization) and broadening (or generalization) of meaning. The paper is based on a lecture held by the author in Maastricht (Klaudy 1996), and further developed in her book Languages in Translation (Klaudy 2003) looking at lexical specification and generalization from a new angle namely from the point of view of universals in translation (Baker 1993, Laviosa 1998).*

Keywords: *lexical transfer operations, generalization, specification, interlanguage asymmetry, universal operations.*

ОБОБЩЕНИЕ И КОНКРЕТИЗАЦИЯ

Аннотация: *Операция лексического переноса, по определению Клауди (2003), представляет собой собирательный термин для всех системных и рутинных оперативных действий, разработанных поколениями переводчиков для преодоления трудностей, возникающих из-за различных лексических систем и культурного контекста двух языков, функционирующих вместе. в процессе перевода. В статье рассматриваются две лексические операции, осуществляемые переводчиками при индоевропейско-венгерском переводе: сужение (или уточнение, конкретизация) и расширение (или обобщение) значения. Статья основана на лекции, прочитанной автором в Маастрихте (Клауди, 1996), и получила дальнейшее развитие в ее книге «Языки в переводе» (Клауди, 2003), рассматривающей лексическую спецификацию и обобщение под новым углом, а именно с точки зрения универсалий в языке. перевод (Бейкер 1993, Лавиоса 1998).*

Ключевые слова: *лексические операции переноса, обобщение, спецификация, межъязыковая асимметрия, универсальные операции.*

Lexical transfer operations

The concept of lexical transfer operations used here is different from the concept of **techniques** (Vinay and Darbelnet 1958/1995, Newmark 1982), **adjustments**, **procedures** (Nida 1964, Nida and Taber 1969), **shifts** (Catford 1965), **lexical transformations** (Shveitser 1973, Retsker 1974, Barkhudarov 1975, Komissarov 1980, 1990, Vaseva 1980), etc. used in the literature.

In our interpretation, "lexical transfer operations" is a collective term for all the systemic and routine-like operative moves developed by generations of translators to handle the difficulties stemming from the different lexical system and cultural context of the two languages functioning together in the process of translation.

Since the lexical systems of different languages reflect human experience in different ways, the lexical transfer operations carried out in translation may shed light on a number of interesting differences between languages. Some of these differences are described by **contrastive lexicography** and are recorded in **bilingual dictionaries**, but the huge number of lexical decisions translators make continuously in the course of their work cannot be foreseen by contrastive lexicographers or recorded in a bilingual dictionary. In investigating lexical operations, we are not concerned with the description of the differences between languages in terms of their lexical systems, but instead with the problem of how these systemic differences are brought into motion in the process of translation, and how they are handled in the daily routine of translators.

In discussing lexical operations, we use the word "lexical" in two senses, referring both to the reason for and the scope of operations. We call them "lexical" because (1) these operations are triggered by the differences in the lexical systems of different languages, and (2) they influence the lexical structure of the sentence.

Lexical operations in translation are seemingly very simple since the translator does nothing more but replace an SL word with a TL word of identical meaning. Yet the term "identical meaning" immediately raises two difficulties. Can any word in any language be identical in its meaning to any other word in any other language? And is it indeed the meaning that has to remain unchanged in the course of translation?

It seems to be firmly embedded in public opinion that in translation it is the meaning that has to remain unchanged. Language teachers frequently advise students to "Translate the sentence so that its meaning is the same as in the original." Even textbooks in linguistics frequently define translation as the replacement of a SL text with a TL text of the same meaning. Meaning is regarded as the invariant of translation also by some translation scholars (Vinay and Darbelnet 1958/1995,

Barkhudarov 1975, Larson 1984)

As even a cursory overview of the problem of meaning in translation would make this introductory section prohibitively long, we shall content ourselves with presenting our interpretation of meaning. **Meaning** is just as much a characteristic of a given language as its formal properties (e.g. morphology and syntax). The meaning of the English word *chair* will never be the same as that of the Uzbek word *stul* since the two linguistic communities relate them to reality according to two different rules of usage. Uzbek *stul* for instance unlike English *chair* cannot be used to refer to a 'the person, who is chosen to preside over a meeting or who is the permanent president of a committee, board'. As meaning in our interpretation is nothing else but the rule of usage of a linguistic sign **within** a given language, it cannot and should not remain unchanged in the process of translation.

What remains unchanged during translation is not the meaning but the **sense**. Sense is not the criteria for the usage of a linguistic sign within a given language, but the relationship between the linguistic sign and a certain segment of reality (objects, events, persons, phenomena) here and now, i.e. an **actual relationship** becoming manifest in a certain communicative situation. It is this relationship that translators **recreate** in the TL instead of retaining the SL meaning. A frequent source of translation errors is that translators try to relate TL signs to reality according to SL rules of usage. This can be successful only very rarely.

Here is a simplified description of the mental operation behind the lexical transfer operation: the translator, who is familiar with the rules by which SL speakers relate SL words to reality (SL meaning), and also with the rules by which TL speakers relate TL words to reality (TL meaning) is looking for a word in the TL with the **same sense**. Having the same sense means that the selected TL item in a **given communicative situation** will be related to the **same segments of reality** by TL speakers, as the SL item. However, to achieve the same sense, the SL meaning will unavoidably undergo various changes. Thus, for example, if the use of the selected TL word is restricted to a narrower circle of things, objects, persons or phenomena, but has the same sense in the given communicative situation, translators consciously or unconsciously will resort to mentally narrowing the SL meaning, or in the reverse case, broaden the SL meaning in the course of translation.

This complex mental activity, leading to lexical choices, generally remains hidden not only for readers of translation but also for translation scholars. Lexical transfer operations will always seem to be simple substitutions. Grammatical transfer operations are more spectacular since the sentence resulting from the translation process has an identical or different structure. In the case

of lexical transfer operations, we can only speculate about the thought processes the translator has gone through in arriving at this seemingly simple lexical substitution

Naturally, it is quite common that a lexical transfer operation is indeed nothing but a simple substitution. In the case of international nomenclature, names of institutions, geographical names, etc., finding the corresponding term in the TL is a matter of identification and not a matter of choice. According to Retsker (1974), translators encounter three kinds of correspondence relationships between SL and TL lexical items: (1) **constant correspondence** where a SL item has only **one** appropriate corresponding lexical item in the TL and the task of the translator is to **find** it; (2) **variant correspondence**, where a SL lexical item appears to have **several** corresponding lexical items in the TL and the task of the translator is to **select** the one that will fit the given situation, and (3) **occasional correspondence**, in which case there is **no** corresponding lexical item in the TL and the task of the translator is to **create** one.

The effort to define a limited number of correspondences may be regarded as a simplified approach to the problems of translation characteristic of early translation studies. Retsker's categories, however, reflect the different degrees of **creativity** in secondary lexical choices. We will not deal here with constant correspondence and substitution, and will discuss only those lexical operations where the translator's task is not simply to find the corresponding TL word, but rather select it, or even create it – as a result of a complex problem-solving and decision-making activity.

Concretization

Lexical narrowing – or, in other terms, **spécification** (Vinay and Darbelnet 1958), **konkretizatsiya** (Retsker 1974, Barkhudarov 1975), **particularisation** (Vinay and Darbelnet 1995) or **concretization** (Klaudy 1996), – is a standard transfer operation whereby the SL unit of a more general meaning is replaced by a TL unit of a more specific meaning. The term specification (or concretisation) is generally discussed together with differentiation since the narrowing of SL meaning is achieved by distinguishing the various meanings of the SL word (differentiation) and then by selecting one of them (specification or concretisation).

Differentiation and specification of meaning in translation can be explained partly by the differences in the mental mapping of the world and by the linguistic consequences of this phenomenon. Individual language communities segment times of the day, various parts of the body, colors, kinship relations, and spatial structures differently. If parts of the body, parts of the day, or kinship relations are more finely subdivided in the TL, i.e. there is a higher number of words in these semantic fields than in the SL, the translator must first identify the meanings of the TL words and

then select one, which will then be narrower than the meaning of the SL word, or to put it in a different way, **more specific**.

Specification can also be explained by differences in the word formation systems of languages. One of the most characteristic features of the Hungarian lexical system is that several productive affixes are used to form verbs. Numerous verbal **ko`makchilar** e.g., *tagida-* ('under'), *bo`ylab-* ('across'), *ichida-* ('in'), *ga-* ('into'), *ichida-* ('in'), *birga-* ('together'), *dan-* ('from'), *aks-* ('counter'), *-dan oldin* ('before'), *oldin* ('before'), *yuqorida* ('up'), *yarim-* ('half'), *yonida* ('aside'), *tepasida* ('above'), etc. and **suffixes** (e.g., frequentative, diminutive, causative, etc) can be fitted to verbs and in this way, new words and new meanings can be created. According to some calculations, there are 40 different frequentative suffixes and 36 **ko`makchilar** indicating instantaneous activity in Uzbek.

With the help of verbal prefixes and suffixes, Hungarian verbs can express the smallest nuances of the same action. If translators want the language of translated Hungarian texts to be as rich as the language of original Hungarian texts, and if they want to make full use of the resources provided by Hungarian, they will probably need to use more specific verbs in Hungarian than those directly triggered by the original IE text.

As the specification of meaning is generally an **optional** transfer operation, which is rarely suggested by bilingual dictionaries, it presupposes some kind of decision-making on the part of translators and can be regarded as a manifestation of the translator's creativity.

The specification of meaning as a standard transfer operation can also be examined from the point of view of so-called "translation universals" (Baker 1993, Laviosa 1998). If we recall Baker's definition of **normalization** as a universal feature of translated texts, specification fits in well with her definition: Normalisation (or "conservativism") is a tendency to exaggerate features of the target language and to conform to its typical patterns" (Baker 1993: 183). Specification in the IE-H direction and generalization in the H-IE direction can be regarded as part of a broader, universal translation strategy of normalization.

The following subtypes of specification will be discussed: (1) Specification of parts of the body, (2) Specification of reporting verbs, (3) Specification of inchoative verbs, (4) Specification of semantically depleted verbs.

Broadening of meaning (generalization)

Lexical broadening – or, in other terms, **généralisation** (Vinay and Darbelnet 1958) **generalization** (Retsker 1974, Barkhudarov 1975), or **generalization** (Vinay and Darbelnet 1995, Klaudy 1996) of meaning – is a standard transfer operation whereby the SL unit of a more specific

meaning is replaced by a TL unit of a more general meaning.

Generalization of meaning in translation can be accounted for differences in the conceptual mapping of the world (body parts, colors, kinship terms) reflected by the different lexical systems of languages. If the SL is characterized by a more detailed segmentation, and there is no dictionary equivalent in the TL, generalization is unavoidable. In the case of generalization, the form of the interlingual asymmetry is manifested as a “many to one” relationship: two or more SL words have one dictionary equivalent in the TL.

Generalization may be needed also because of differences in the word-formation systems of languages. The rich inventory of verbal prefixes and suffixes in Hungarian makes it possible to form verbs with a high degree of semantic compression. Semantically rich Hungarian verbs, which have no dictionary equivalents of similar semantic compression in IE languages, will become either more general in translation or will be translated by several words (cf. distribution of meaning (Klaudy 2003: 223-232).

Generalization of meaning as a transfer operation can also be examined from the point of view of a universal translation strategy, **simplification**. Simplification is one of the supposed universal characteristics of translated texts (Baker 1993, Laviosa 1998). Two reasons seem to underpin the universal character of generalization: (1) it is easier **to find** a TL correspondent with a more general meaning, and (2) it is easier **to fit** a TL correspondent with a more general meaning into the structure of the TL sentence.

The following subtypes of generalization will be discussed: (1) Generalisation of parts of the body, (2) Generalisation of times of the day, (3) Generalisation of realia, (4) Generalisation of semantically rich verbs.

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